

CERTIFICATE OF APPRECIATION

TIBBIYOT AKADEMIYASI
JURNALIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

Rakhimov Dilmurodjon Adilzhanovich

LEUKOPLAKIA CLINIC , DIAGNOSIS , TREATMENT

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN
TAQDIRLANADI

WWW.REANDPUB.UZ

